

Foliar application of polyamines, kinetin, and ascorbic acid and rice grain filling

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We examined rate of grain filling when polyamines, kinetin, and ascorbic acid were applied at preflowering. Three-day-old pregerminated cultivar GR3 seeds were sown in 8 kg puddled soils in plastic pots. Plants were thinned to three per pot. At 45, 47, 49, and 51 d after sowing, 10 μmol of the polyamines putrescine, spermidine, and spermine and 2 ppm of kinetin were sprayed on the test plants. Rate of grain filling after panicle emergence was measured gravimetrically.

Polyamine, kinetin, or ascorbic acid brought about early grain maturity (indicated by early optimum fresh weight compared to control) (see figure).

Effect of polyamines, kinetin, and ascorbic acid on grain filling in rice cultivar G-R3. Baroda, India.

Initial rate of filling was higher in all treatments. However, 6 d after panicle emergence, rate of supply from source to sink in the ascorbic acid treatment decreased dramatically, and those plants yielded less than control. In the kinetin

treatment, rate of grain filling was higher (as indicated by fresh weight) on day 6, but final yield did not differ from control. In the polyamine treatments, rate filling was far superior. □

Contribution of aquatic tillers to grain yield in deepwater rice

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Aquatic tillers in deepwater rice can contribute considerably to grain yield, if the water level rises early in the rainy season and peaks 4-8 wk before flowering.

To assess the contribution of aquatic tillers to grain yield, floating rices Desaria 8 and Jaladhi 1, deepwater rice Parwapankh, and 2 cultivation methods — direct seeding the last week of May and transplanting 60-d-old seedlings the first week of Sep 1983 — were studied in a randomized block design with 3 replications in the BAC farm tank. Plot size was 9 × 4 m.

More aquatic tillers were formed in transplanted than in direct seeded rice (see table). Direct-seeded rice suffered a long dry spell during early growth and

Aquatic tillers, height, panicle length, and percentage contribution of aquatic tillers to single plant yield in transplanted (T) and direct seeded (D) deepwater rices. Bihar, India, 1983.

Variety	Cultivation method	Aquatic tillers (no.)	Tiller height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Contribution (%) of aquatic tillers to single plant yield
Desaria 8	T	2.7	80.2	14.3	54.9
	D	1.2	279.7	24.4	26.9
Jaladhi 1	T	2.5	71.2	16.3	54.9
	D	1.5	152.0	24.0	13.9
Parwapankh	T	4.0	61.2	16.4	44.2
	D	1.0	118.6	23.0	14.5
CD		0.2	—	0.8	7.5

produced more basal tillers. Transplanting was done in 25-30 cm deep water that inhibited production of basal tillers. To compensate, the plants produced greater numbers of aquatic tillers. Highest average number of aquatic tillers was in transplanted Parwapankh.

The longest aquatic tiller (279.7 cm) was in direct seeded Desaria 8, the shortest (61.2 cm) in transplanted Parwapankh. The longest panicle (24.4 cm) was in direct seeded Desaria 8,

and the shortest (14.3 cm) in transplanted Desaria 8.

Contribution of aquatic tillers to grain yield was highest in transplanted rice. □

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